

Supplementary Materials for the Paper: NK Hybrid Genetic Algorithm for Clustering

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Table S 1: Evaluation ($f(\mathbf{x})$) of the best solutions for 4 clustering algorithms for datasets generated from the Gaussian model with noise. The algorithms are: k-means, DBSCAN, DP, and NK hybrid GA. All solutions are evaluated using DBCV. The average ARI, over 9 datasets (3 random datasets for each one of the 3 levels of balance) for each combination of N_c and l , for the best partitions is presented.

N_c	l	k-means	DBSCAN	DP	NK hybrid GA
2	2	0.5271 $\pm$ 0.5546	0.4357 $\pm$ 0.4338	0.1320 $\pm$ 0.1029	0.2123 $\pm$ 0.1957
2	5	0.1355 $\pm$ 0.1022	0.7591 $\pm$ 0.2426	0.1357 $\pm$ 0.1023	0.1526 $\pm$ 0.1564
5	2	0.0233 $\pm$ 0.0079	0.0256 $\pm$ 0.0092	0.0640 $\pm$ 0.0650	0.0895 $\pm$ 0.0388
5	5	0.0502 $\pm$ 0.0325	0.0867 $\pm$ 0.0835	0.1027 $\pm$ 0.1327	0.0617 $\pm$ 0.0325
8	2	0.0642 $\pm$ 0.0309	0.0518 $\pm$ 0.0177	0.0619 $\pm$ 0.0529	0.0786 $\pm$ 0.0477
8	5	0.1229 $\pm$ 0.0876	0.0265 $\pm$ 0.0056	0.1958 $\pm$ 0.1564	0.0265 $\pm$ 0.0058
11	2	0.0896 $\pm$ 0.0516	0.0373 $\pm$ 0.0164	0.1348 $\pm$ 0.0923	0.0359 $\pm$ 0.0157
11	5	0.1352 $\pm$ 0.1086	0.0215 $\pm$ 0.0046	0.1505 $\pm$ 0.1645	0.0197 $\pm$ 0.0048

Table S 2: Evaluation ($f(\mathbf{x})$) of the best solutions for 4 clustering algorithms for shape datasets. All solutions are evaluated using DBCV.

Problem	k-means	DBSCAN	DP	NK hybrid GA
Aggregation	0.6734	0.5623	0.2217	0.2482
Zahns Compound	0.2063	0.6976	0.2445	0.4047
Flame	0.8072	0.8986	0.5309	0.1659
A.K. Jains Toy Problem	0.7852	0.6267	0.6228	0.8890
Path-based1	0.4949	0.7253	0.3955	0.8366
R15	0.0290	0.0290	0.2190	0.1489
Path-based 2 (Spiral)	1.2324	0.2355	0.4433	0.4340

Table S 3: Evaluation ($f(\mathbf{x})$) of the best solutions for 4 clustering algorithms for UCI machine learning datasets. All solutions are evaluated using DBCV.

Problem	k-means	DBSCAN	DP	NK hybrid GA
Iris	0.8062	0.5111	0.1259	0.6267
Glass	0.5997	0.5922	0.8488	0.3708
Ionosphere	1.6110	1.0000	0.7861	0.4686
Ecoli	1.3851	0.6602	0.4833	1.1158

Table S 4: Evaluation ($f(\mathbf{x})$) of the best solutions for 4 clustering algorithms for datasets generated from the Gaussian model with noise. All solutions are evaluated using NKCV with $K = 3$.

N_c	l	k-means	DBSCAN	DP	NK hybrid GA
2	2	0.0038 $\pm$ 0.0055	0.0028 $\pm$ 0.0030	0.0028 $\pm$ 0.0030	0.0025 $\pm$ 0.0027
2	5	0.0085 $\pm$ 0.0074	0.0086 $\pm$ 0.0077	0.0085 $\pm$ 0.0075	0.0069 $\pm$ 0.0062
5	2	0.0005 $\pm$ 0.0003	0.0003 $\pm$ 0.0001	0.0006 $\pm$ 0.0003	0.0002 $\pm$ 0.0000
5	5	0.0010 $\pm$ 0.0006	0.0009 $\pm$ 0.0006	0.0011 $\pm$ 0.0006	0.0003 $\pm$ 0.0002
8	2	0.0006 $\pm$ 0.0004	0.0005 $\pm$ 0.0003	0.0005 $\pm$ 0.0002	0.0003 $\pm$ 0.0001
8	5	0.0011 $\pm$ 0.0004	0.0001 $\pm$ 0.0001	0.0013 $\pm$ 0.0005	0.0001 $\pm$ 0.0001
11	2	0.0006 $\pm$ 0.0003	0.0003 $\pm$ 0.0002	0.0009 $\pm$ 0.0006	0.0002 $\pm$ 0.0001
11	5	0.0007 $\pm$ 0.0006	0.0001 $\pm$ 0.0002	0.0008 $\pm$ 0.0006	0.0001 $\pm$ 0.0001

Table S 5: ARI for the solutions found by the 4 clustering algorithms for datasets generated from the Gaussian model with noise. All solutions are evaluated using NKCV with $K = 3$.

N_c	l	k-means	DBSCAN	DP	NK hybrid GA
2	2	0.90 $\pm$ 0.19	0.54 $\pm$ 0.51	0.97 $\pm$ 0.01	0.95 $\pm$ 0.04
2	5	0.97 $\pm$ 0.01	0.01 $\pm$ 0.02	0.97 $\pm$ 0.01	0.96 $\pm$ 0.04
5	2	0.93 $\pm$ 0.10	0.83 $\pm$ 0.11	0.88 $\pm$ 0.14	0.99 $\pm$ 0.00
5	5	0.96 $\pm$ 0.07	0.81 $\pm$ 0.23	0.82 $\pm$ 0.33	1.00 $\pm$ 0.00
8	2	0.86 $\pm$ 0.13	0.69 $\pm$ 0.13	0.83 $\pm$ 0.10	0.87 $\pm$ 0.11
8	5	0.76 $\pm$ 0.24	1.00 $\pm$ 0.00	0.88 $\pm$ 0.11	1.00 $\pm$ 0.00
11	2	0.94 $\pm$ 0.04	0.95 $\pm$ 0.06	0.73 $\pm$ 0.22	0.95 $\pm$ 0.05
11	5	0.92 $\pm$ 0.06	0.98 $\pm$ 0.04	0.93 $\pm$ 0.08	0.98 $\pm$ 0.04

Table S 6: Evaluation ($f(\mathbf{x})$) of the best solutions for 4 clustering algorithms for shape datasets. All solutions are evaluated using NKCV with $K = 3$.

Problem	k-means	DBSCAN	DP	NK hybrid GA
Aggregation	0.0087	0.0048	0.0040	0.0037
Zahns Compound	0.0049	0.0062	0.0051	0.0033
Flame	0.0185	0.0079	0.0079	0.0070
A.K. Jains Toy Problem	0.0102	0.0100	0.0100	0.0058
Path-based1	0.0085	0.0086	0.0077	0.0068
R15	0.0014	0.0028	0.0033	0.0012
Path-based 2 (Spiral)	0.0204	0.0150	0.0130	0.0128

Table S 7: ARI for the solutions found by the 4 clustering algorithms for shape datasets. All solutions are evaluated using NKCV with $K = 3$.

Problem	k-means	DBSCAN	DP	NK hybrid GA
Aggregation	0.67	0.06	0.49	0.99
Zahns Compound	0.74	0.00	0.59	0.88
Flame	0.45	0.00	0.00	0.01
A.K. Jains Toy Problem	0.26	0.00	0.00	0.19
Path-based1	0.40	0.00	0.47	0.57
R15	0.99	0.26	0.20	0.87
Path-based 2 (Spiral)	-0.00	0.00	1.00	0.99

Table S 8: Evaluation ($f(\mathbf{x})$) of the best solutions for 4 clustering algorithms for UCI machine learning datasets. All solutions are evaluated using NKCV with $K = 3$.

Problem	k-means	DBSCAN	DP	NK hybrid GA
Iris	0.0087	0.0094	0.0080	0.0076
Glass	0.0011	0.0025	0.0015	0.0002
Ionosphere	0.0058	0.0053	0.0053	0.0014
Ecoli	0.0082	0.0084	0.0084	0.0058

Table S 9: ARI for the solutions found by the 4 clustering algorithms for UCI machine learning datasets. All solutions are evaluated using NKCV with $K = 3$.

Problem	k-means	DBSCAN	DP	NK hybrid GA
Iris	0.54	0.00	0.57	0.55
Glass	0.25	0.01	0.21	0.18
Ionosphere	0.18	0.00	0.00	0.32
Ecoli	0.38	0.00	0.00	0.47

Table S 10: Maximum outdegree (K_{out}) in the experiments with $K = 3$. The correlation coefficients, when compared to K_{out} , are: 0.2893 for N , 0.0205 for N_c , and 0.6787 for l .

Problem	N	N_c	l	K_{out}
Gaussian	800	2	2	9
			5	12
			2	10
			5	13
			8	9
			8	13
			11	9
			11	14
Iris	150	3	4	11
Glass	124	6	9	8
Ionosphere	351	2	34	17
Ecoli	336	8	7	9
Aggregation	788	7	2	7
Zahns Compound	399	6		7
Flame	240	2		7
A.K. Jains Toy Prob.	373	2		8
Path-based 1	300	3		8
R15	600	15		9
Path-based 2 (Spiral)	312	3		6

Table S 11: ARI for the solutions found by the 4 clustering algorithms for the G2 datasets with standard deviation equal to 30 and with different number of attributes (l). The G2 datasets are generated using two Gaussian normal distributions. All solutions are evaluated using DBCV. The GA was executed for $3N/2$ seconds.

l	N	N_c	k-means	DBSCAN	DP	NK hybrid GA
16	2,048	2	1.00	0.31	1.00	0.83
32			1.00	0.26	1.00	0.82
64			1.00	0.21	1.00	0.84
128			1.00	0.54	1.00	0.89
256			1.00	0.55	1.00	0.95
512			1.00	0.54	1.00	0.98
1024			1.00	0.55	1.00	1.00

Figure S 1: Example of recombination by PX in a dataset with $N = 500$ and $l = 2$.

Figure S 2: Results for the first dataset generated from the Gaussian model with noise with parameters: $N_c = 2$, $l = 2$, second balance level. The partitions presented in all figures are the best partitions found by each algorithm according to $\mathcal{D}_{BCV}$. The optimal solutions and the interaction graph are also presented.

Figure S 3: Results for the first dataset generated from the Gaussian model with noise with parameters: $N_c = 5$, $l = 2$, second balance level.

Figure S 4: Results for the first dataset generated from the Gaussian model with noise with parameters: $N_c = 8$, $l = 2$, second balance level.

Figure S 5: Results for the first dataset generated from the Gaussian model with noise with parameters: $N_c = 11$, $l = 2$, second balance level.

Figure S 6: Results for dataset Aggregation.

Figure S 7: Results for dataset Zahns Compound.

Figure S 8: Results for dataset Flame.

Figure S 9: Results for dataset A.K. Jains Toy Problem.

Figure S 10: Results for dataset Path-based 1.

Figure S 11: Results for dataset R15.

Figure S 12: Results for dataset Path-based 2 (Spiral).

